

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8227651

IDENTIFICATION OF PIGMENTS ON THE 19th CENTURY FRENCH SHELL PATTERN IN MARBLING PAPER: ANALYTICAL STUDY

Wafika Noshy Wahba¹, Rushdya Rabee Ali Hassan¹, Amira Yehia Abd El Wahab
Mahmoud² and Eman Salim¹

¹*Restoration and Conservation Department, Faculty of Archaeology, Cairo University, 12613 Giza, Egypt*

²*Conservator in the Ministry of Tourism and Antiquities, Cairo, Egypt*

Received: 11/05/2023

Accepted: 08/08/2023

Corresponding author: Eman Salim (emansalim@cu.edu.eg)

ABSTRACT

The study aims to examine and analyze one of the most famous marble papers in pattern, which is the French shell pattern; the latter is dated to the late 18th century in France. It also aims to accurately determine the nature and chemical composition of the colours, especially due to the scarcity of studies related to the art of historical Ebru. The morphology of marbling paper (Ebru) samples was investigated by Digi micro -USB microscope and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) with energy-dispersive X-ray analysis (EDX). Furthermore, the Raman microscopy technique detected the type of pigments or dyes used in this paper. The results revealed that inorganic pigments were used to manufacture ebru art, eliminating the widespread belief that organic pigments were the basis for decorating this type of art. Despite the splendour of the ebru art, it is a completely forgotten art that did not take a share of the study. The current study sheds light on the nature of the chemical composition of the colours used, especially because of the conflict between scientists about the use of dyes or inorganic pigments in the technique of this vanished art.

KEYWORDS: Ebru, Marbling paper, SEM, EDX, Raman, French shell, pigments

1. INTRODUCTION

Investigating archaeological objects provides further information on development technology. Carrying out the conservation and restoration of these objects necessitates that understand their crystal structures and chemical constituents should be understood. Marbling (Ebru) is an elegant art used to decorate paper for calligraphy and bookbinding not often met in scientific literature. Traditional marbling techniques, colors, and other existing materials may provide several facts and historical information on this technique.

Ebru relies on Japanese and Ottoman traditions. By the mid-sixteenth century, it arrived in Western Europe and began to spread carefully to other areas, including England and France, in the 18th century (Pazar, 2016 and Chambers, 1993).

Since the 19th century, marbled papers became an indispensable part of almost every book published, and rivals rushed to publish other books on the subject. By the end of the 19th century, marbling was a popular and widely practiced art form. However, as machines replaced hand binding, marbling soon became passé, and its popularity declined. By the beginning of the 20th century, marbling was nearly a lost art. Nevertheless, Ebru, similar to the case of hand-made books and papermaking, has been revived by artists and calligraphers (Gruber, 2001 and Guyot, 1988; Benson, J. (2019).

Ebru is deeply rooted in history and may utilize several materials (Pazar, 2016) compared to other decorated papers (Sönmez, 2016; Gurber, 2001). Nevertheless, its major idea is almost the same across techniques and materials.

Several cultures expanded their own technique for paper marbling, e.g., Chinese marbling, Japanese Suminagashi, Turkish Ebru marbling, European marbling, and marbling of Islamic calligraphy. For a long time, the main technique of Ebru has been based on a heavier liquid (size) made by mixing gum tragacanth or Irish moss plant (carrageenan) with water and poured into a shallow rectangular vessel, a marbling tray, with the approximate dimensions of the paper (Halfer, 1894 and Easton, 1983).

After that, prepared dyes or pigments are dropped or spattered onto the size with a brush. Colors floating in the tray are then stirred with straws, styluses, or special combs to create intricate designs on size and get ready to put them on paper. Next, the paper is lifted off carefully the size and left to dry. Finally, the marbled paper is ready after drying and smoothing (Sönmez, 2016; Grunebaum, 1984).

This project looks at one of the marbled paper patterns in France called "French shell" or "shell marbling", which is used for many book parts, e.g., endpapers, covers, and text blocks' edges (Pazar, 2016; Behrens, 2015; Rubovits, 1992).

This pattern dates to the late eighteenth century in France, like the Turkish one. In this pattern, all colors have a ground with a preparation of beeswax, rated (1 pound: 1 ounce) to protect the color from rubbing off and polish it. After choosing the desired colors, they will be sprinkled onto the water bath. Moreover, some oil drops are added to the gall and can be mixed and stirred up well with a brush every time the artist adds this oil (Loring, 1952; Shannon, 1987). This shall be sometimes tried to obtain the required impact, namely having shell-like rings that are less dark around the edges than in the center (Maurer, and Maurer, 1984, 1899). The artists must carefully mix the oil because adding much oil can result in losing the ringed or shell appearance entirely, whereas adding a little will make the object full of unsightly holes. Spreading out with much oil can ruin the entire pattern. Accordingly, mixing more color with no oil is the only manner of resolving this issue (Woolnough, 1881). Several works have been reported since the last century on the marble paper (Maurer-Mathison and Philippoff, 1993; Schmoller, 1987; Nevins, 1989)

There is a lack of scientific studies of the pigments and materials used for marbling paper in different eras, despite the many studies of the pigments used on Islamic illuminated manuscripts. Only three early French essays were written on paper marbling dating from 1642 to 1765: French bookbinders were the first Europeans to study and use marbled paper in book arts. Wolfe (1990) reported the history of producing and using marbled paper. Special attention is also paid to the various technical processes of the manufacture and the origins of many patterns of marbling. Woolnough (1881) Woolnough was probably the greatest English writer on the marble of the 18th century and the first to write an English manual on marbling, the art of marbling. This book was a reprint of a lecture he presented in 1878 to the Royal Arts Society (Schleicher, and Schleicher, 1993; Mathison, 1899).

Various techniques of analysis may be applied to determine pigments and paper-based materials for the pigment layer, i.e., atomic absorption, infrared spectroscopy, laser and electron microprobe analysis, XRD, and XRF. Raman microscopy is a non-destructive method that can be applied to identify pigments and dyes on all artworks. It is an appropriate technique since it gives more information about the range of pigments used in illuminating paper manuscripts.

The aim of the present investigation concerns a printed book explaining agriculture written in French and dating back to the 19th century. Microanalyses using non-invasive techniques, such as scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy-dispersive X-ray analysis (EDX), and Raman spectroscopy, were carried out in the present study to detect the technique of paper marbling, identify the colours palette used for marbling paper in this pattern dating back to the 19th century, determine the type of paper, and investigate the condition of preservation.

2. METHODS AND SAMPLES

2.1 Sampling

Samples were collected from a printed book explaining agriculture written in French and dating back to the 19th century. Five samples were carefully collected for the microanalysis, representing the red, yellow, blue, brown, and black colors.

2.2 Visual observations

Preparatory observations on the morphology of marbled paper were employed using a Digi micro - USB microscope mit 500 with a monitor of 5 MP Digital zoom (maximum) Technology Co., Ltd. Co. WR-10QC model was employed to examine the color layer.

2.3 Raman microscopy

Raman microscopy was carried out using a Raman confocal microscope, Bruker Senterra 11, magnification 20 x, Resolution 4 cm⁻¹, Laser 785nm Power 1microwatt. Neutral filters were used to avoid damage to paper samples. The illuminating and collecting optics of the system consisted of a microscope in the confocal configuration (a special long working distance of 20x objective). The laser beam's power was set to less than 5 mw on the sample using a set of neutral density filters. Green and red exciting frequencies were utilized to collect the spectra. Because of the good optical features of commercial laser beams, a small sample color layer could be analyzed.

2.4 SEM -EDX analysis

SEM-EDX was employed for color analysis. Paper samples were examined uncoated, using a variable pressure SEM (FEL Quanta 3D 200i Edx / Thermo

fisher pathfinder, with the following conditions, including low vacuum for acceleration voltage 20.0~30.0 kv by large field detector with 15~17 mm working distance. The electron beam was adjusted ~400 PA for generating adequate X-rays to enable good identification of EDS peaks, keep down spectral artifacts, and attain detector < 20%. The beam spot size was (5- 30).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Visual observations

Examination with the digital microscope showed the outer shape of the surface of the fibers, where we can observe the overlapping of the pigment particles inside the paper structure. Moreover, it is possible to notice erosion and lacerations in the paper fibers in some places, as shown in (Fig. 1).

3.2 Raman spectroscopy microscope

Raman spectroscopy was used to identify pigment layers. The red pigments which were widely used were hematite (iron oxide) also called red ochre; red lead (lead oxide) also called minium, and vermilion or cinnabar (Medeiros, 1994; Miura, 1991). Fig. 2 represents Raman spectra collected on marbled paper on a red spot. The spectra were registered on the chromatic pattern. Minimum stretching bands corresponding to Pb -O were observed at 547 cm⁻¹; while the O-Pb deformation mode was observed at 118 cm⁻¹, suggesting the use of red lead. During the ancient and medieval periods, people used red lead for decoration and printing purposes (Maurcci et al., 2018). The EDX spectrum (Fig. 2) represents characteristic peaks of lead as the main element confirmed that the red color used was red lead. Lead oxides were one of the earliest artificial pigments and one of the most widely used during this period. Red lead (minium) Pb₃O₄ was mainly an orange-red pigment prepared by heating red lead or lead carbonate at high temperatures (Nastova et al., 2012). Minimum exists in crystalline or amorphous form due to the manufacturing process. It is a color with high covering power, high adhesion to the substrate, and insoluble in water. Red lead was detected in paintings dating back to the 11th to the 19th centuries in Europe and India and used on different types of writing supports, such as illuminating manuscripts, wood panels, and paper.

Figure 1. Digital micrographs of the marbled paper samples show the main colors used in marbling paper. It can be seen the marbled pattern of the French shell in different colors; A & B: give a much clearer image of the brown, red, blue, and black colors in a stone marble pattern; C & D: show the yellow and black colors obviously; E & F: reveal the fading of the blue and flaking of red color spots. Also, the inorganic nature of the colors used in the pattern can be detected.

Figure 2. Raman spectrum of the red color's surface, showing the characteristic peaks of red lead; stretching bands corresponding to Pb-O are observed at 547cm^{-1} .

Yellow color

Chrome yellow is a class of pigments widely used by painters and calligraphers and is known for its several chemical stability; it has the pure lead chromate (PbCrO_4) found in nature as the mineral crocoite.

According to the literature, chrome yellow has a strong peak at 840cm^{-1} because of the Cr-O stretching and bending modes, which appear at around 840

cm^{-1} to 875cm^{-1} and 880cm^{-1} , as reported in Fig. 3. The chromate CrO_4 bending mode located at around $280\text{--}400\text{cm}^{-1}$ and the signal at around 340cm^{-1} corresponds to the CrO_4 . The band located at 360cm^{-1} suggests PbCrO_4 . Chromium Cr was clearly detected by EDX microanalysis. Furthermore, no lead Pb was observed in the examined sample.

Figure 3. Raman spectrum on the yellow color's surface, showing bands of chrome yellow observed at 360 and 840 cm^{-1}

Blue color

Raman spectrum collected from the blue spot (Fig. 4) revealed the characteristic bands of Prussian blue from around 2155 cm^{-1} to 2160 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the CN stretching mode. Other representative peaks in the range (550-620 cm^{-1}) are attributed to the Fe-C stretching mode. According to the literature (Woolnough, 1881), Prussian blue is brighter and

darker than Chinese blue. Regarding EDX microanalysis, using Prussian blue combined with white lead is expected. Using synthetic instead of natural ultramarine was highlighted by the round shape and fine particles' size. In the 1700s, Prussian blue was manufactured in Berlin. According to the literature on pigment, history reported that Prussian blue pigment was not used before the 1720s.

Figure 4. Raman spectrum of the blue color, showing the characteristic bands of Prussian blue at around 2155 cm^{-1} to 2160 cm^{-1} corresponding to the CN stretching mode

Black color

Vegetable black represents a higher type of lamp black, manufactured from vegetable substance and extensively found in the darkest spots of the pattern of French shell. The Raman of the black color spots

analyzed in this study consistently gave rise to a Raman spectrum (Fig. 5). We could notice that Raman bands were recorded at 934 cm^{-1} and 962 cm^{-1} , attributed to symmetric stretching bands of phosphate that may be due to the animal origin of the carbon black (Koochakzaei et al., 2022).

Figure 5. Raman spectrum of the black color, the spectral regions between 3500 and 500 cm^{-1} , the spectrum represents bands at 1584 cm^{-1} which are due to the presence of carbon black. We can notice that Raman bands were recorded at 934 cm^{-1} and 962 cm^{-1} , the stretching band of phosphate. These may be due to the animal origin of the carbon black.

Brown color

When analyzing the brown spot using Raman spectra, it was found that it is an unsuitable technique for brown color due to the possibility of the presence of many organic substances (Fig. 6). So, there is a possibility that the color resulting from mixing the red

color used in this pattern, which was likely to be a lead oxide (Minimum), detected with stretching bands corresponding to Pb-O was observed at 547 cm^{-1} (Maurcci et al., 2018), with the black color which was likely to be carbon black.

Figure 6. Raman spectrum of brown color obtained on the red color, showing the characteristic peaks of red lead; stretching bands corresponding to Pb-O are observed at 547 cm^{-1} , and Raman spectra of the black color are recorded at 934 cm^{-1} and 962 cm^{-1} the stretching band of phosphate; these may be due to the animal origin of the carbon black.

3.3. SEM and EDX microanalysis

Paper contains invariable concentrations of inorganic substances. During the manufacturing process, additives, such as ion salts used as fillers like clay or carbonate salts, sizing substances or traces, like mineral compounds in the case of chromatic area, are added to the paper in order to obtain specific pattern (Bicchieri et al., 2019). The presence of metal salts may

be due to many reasons, resulting from the use of contaminated water with heavy metal or the use of rusty molds. SEM images (Fig. 7) represent the outer surface of marbled paper samples. The red color area displayed the fine-grained layer that appeared with fine cracks at (2000 \times , scale bar 50 μm). The morphology of a yellow spot showed fine cracks on the chromatic layer, the blue color showed a fine grain layer, while the black color area showed a fine homogeneous layer (Fig. 8).

Figure 7. SEM images picked up from the outer surface of the marbled paper samples; A& B: the red colour area, fine grained layer with fine cracks are observed at (2000 x, scale bar 50 μm); C& D: Morphology of a yellow spot, one can see fine cracks on the chromatic layer; E& F: Fine grains of the blue pigment.

Figure 8. SEM images picked up from the outer surface of the marbled paper sample; A&B: the turquoise colour in two tones at (2000 x, scale bar 50 μm); C& D: a black colour spot, one can see a fine homogeneous layer; E: the fibre bundles from uncoated sample.

Red color

The most traditional red colors used for marbling paper in the 19th century were vermilion, hematite, and red lead (Chambers, 1993). They were mixed with each other or with other colours to alter the tone

of the main colour. A characteristic ESEM image picked up from a red colour spot is given in (Fig. 9). The EDX microanalysis recorded on the red spot of the sample showed a significant percentage of Pb. Also, insignificant elements, such as silicon, aluminium, sodium, potassium, and sulfur, were recorded

with minor traces of iron, magnesium, and chlorine. The red colour in the sample contained a significant percentage of calcium and aluminum, with minor traces of Si, Cl, and K. Therefore, the red pigment consisted of the red lead side with some natural deposits in the stone used (Ardelean *et al.*, 2013).

EDX spectrum of the paper sample showed considerable elemental composition with a high silicon and

oxygen content. The negligible concentration of S and Al might be due to the presence of alum used as a solution to coat and prepare the surface of the paper before printing. It was also necessary for making the size for the paper after marbling. The sulphur, carbon, and calcium were possibly due to inorganic filling (Cosentino, 2014).

Figure 9. EDX spectrum of the red pigment, representing characteristic peaks of carbon, lead, and minor traces of iron.

Yellow color

The yellow pigment in the marbled paper sample was mainly composed of chrome yellow: EDX spectrum of the yellow spot (Fig. 10) showed a large chrome peak with significant carbon, oxygen, and lead peaks. This might indicate chrome yellow pigment, which was extremely used to obtain different

shades of yellow, namely lemon, middle, and orange, ranging from deep orange to pale lemon (Woolnough, 1881). Chrome yellow is lead chromate (PbCrO_4), which occurs naturally as mineral crocoites. It is the primary ingredient of chrome yellow mixed with Prussian blue in chrome green. It was employed in the 2nd quarter of the 19th century.

Figure 10. Spectrum obtained via SEM-EDX microanalysis, with the characteristic peaks of lead chromate.

Blue color

The composition of these pigments contains a high percentage of lead in the examined sample, possibly related to white lead that was added to obtain bright colours. White lead represents a major white pigment

used in illuminated manuscripts. It is generally used with other colours to improve their characteristics. It was mainly mixed with blue pigments to obtain bright and stable colours (Alireza *et al.*, 2022). Considering the presence of iron and nitrogen elements,

as shown in (Fig. 11), the possibility of using Prussian blue $\text{Fe}_4[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]_{3-16} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ in combination with white lead is expected. Using synthetic instead of natural ultramarine was highlighted by the round shape

and fine particles' size. In the 1700s, Diesbach developed Prussian blue in Berlin. The Prussian blue pigment was employed in the 19th century Chinese painting, replacing the azurite blue and natural indigo used in the 18th century.

Figure 11. Spectrum obtained via SEM-EDX microanalysis, with the characteristic peaks of lead and iron; the spectrum corresponding to Prussian blue pigment.

Black color

The EDX analysis of the black spots (Fig.12) revealed a representative C peak, the percent of C as a major component of 46.38%. The combined detection of Ca and P and the presence of higher content of Mg might reveal the black colour used for marbling paper. The black carbon-based black substances were used as the main black pigment for marbling paper.

Bone black pigments are a superior kind of black, impure pigment manufactured by charring animal bone. The elemental composition showed significant ratios of (C, Na, Mg, Al, Si, P, K, Cl, and S). The presence of aluminium and sulphur indicated the presence of Alum used as a solution to coat and prepare the surface of the paper before printing (Keheyani and Baraldi, 2015).

Figure 12. Spectrum obtained via SEM-EDX microanalysis, corresponding to carbon black pigment, a representative of the C peak.

Brown color

The EDX data of the brown pigment sample illustrated that the elemental composition of this brown pigment included (C, O, Pb, Ca, Si, Mg, Na, S, Cl, K, and F), as shown in (Fig.13). Black and red colours were mixed to produce the brown color and used in the French shell for this period, as is evident. Thus, EDX data illustrated the elemental composition of the

red pigment, probably composed of Pb and O, indicating that Pb_3O_4 was employed as the red pigment extensively in the implementation of the Ebru in this period (Woolnough, 1881). The EDX analysis of the black colour revealed a representative C peak, the percent of C as a major component of 46.38% of the black colour used for marbling paper. Carbon-based black substances were used as the main black pigment for marbling paper in different era.

Figure 13. Spectrum obtained via SEM –EDX microanalysis, representing significant elements detected, which indicates the inorganic pigment; the spectrum represents characteristic peaks of carbon and lead and minor traces of iron to obtain the brown colour.

4. CONCLUSION

The identification of pigments on the 19th century French shell pattern in marbling has provided excellent results which have proved that most of the pigments used are of inorganic origins, such as the black pigment consisting of a black lamp, the blue pigment from Prussian blue, and finally, the yellow pigment from lead chromate. Moreover, the red pigment consists of red lead with some natural deposits in the stone used. The artist also mixed the black and red colours to produce the brown pigment, characteristic of the French shell pattern.

EDX results illustrated that the paper contained invariable concentrations of inorganic substances. During the manufacturing process, additives were added, such as ion salts used as fillers like clay or carbonate salts, sizing substances or traces, like mineral compounds in the case of chromatic area, or added to the paper in order to obtain the specific pattern. The present case study also concludes that Raman analysis is not useful for fully characterizing the selected pigments, especially the natural organic dyes that are challenging for the researchers. This highlights the possibility of using other techniques that can give more identity information.

AUTHORS CONTRIBUTION: A.M collected the historical samples for pigment identification, and participated in the writing of the research. E.S discussed the results of Raman & EDX analyses, and participated in the writing. W.N read and reviewed the article. R.H participated in the writing the research. All authors reviewed and approved the article.

REFERENCES

- Alireza, K., Samane A., Bidgoli B., (2022) Identification of pigments used in Qajar manuscript from Iran by using atomic and molecular spectroscopy and technical photography methods, *Journal of Heritage Science*, Vol 10, No.30, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40494-022-00665-x>
- Ardelean E., Melniciuc N., Vornicu N., (2013) Red pigments used for writing and illuminating manuscripts, I: *Analele Ştiinţifice ale Universităţii »Alexandru Ioan Cuza« din Iaşi. Teologie Ortodoxă*, pp. 75-87.
- Behrens, K. (2015) *The history and techniques of marble paper*, <http://blog.books.tell.youwhy.com/>; <https://blog.bookstellyouwhy.com/the-history-and-techniques-of-marbled-paper>.
- Benson, J. (2019) Curious Colors of Currency: Security Marbling on Financial Instruments During the Long Eighteenth Century. *American Journal of Numismatics*, 31: 277–325, (Plates 37–27).
- Chambers, A (1993) *Suminagashi: The Japanese art of marbling: A practical guide*. Thames & Hudson; Reprint edition, London.
- Cosentino, A. (2014) Identification of pigments by multispectral imaging; a flowchart method, *Herit Sci.* 2, 8 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1186/2050-7445-2-8>.
- Easton, P. J. (1983) *Marbling, A history and bibliography*. Los Angeles: Dawson's Bookshop.
- Grunebaum, G (1984) *How to marbelize paper; Step-by-Step instructions for 12 traditional patterns*. New York: Dover Publications, Inc.
- Gurber, D. (2001) *Marbling on a Budget*. Arts & Activities. November.
- Guyot, D (1988) *Suminagashi: An Introduction to Japanese Marbling*. Seattle Brass Galley Press.

- Halfer, J. (1894) *The Progress of the Marbling Art*. Buffalo: American Bookbinding.
- Keheyany Y. and Baraldi P. (2015) The use of non-invasive micro-Raman, FTIR and SEM EDX analyses to study Armenian illuminated manuscripts, Conference: Technart 15, Catania, Italy, pp.1.
- Loring, R. B. (1952) *Decorated book papers; being an account of their designs and fashions*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
- Maurer, D. V & Maurer, P (1899) *Marbling: A complete guide to creating beautiful patterned papers and fabrics*. Friedman/Fairfax Pub.
- Maurer, D.P and Maurer, P. (1984) *An Introduction to Carrageenan and Watercolor Marbling*. Centre Hall, PA, by Diane Maurer and Paul Maurer.
- Maurer-Mathison, D and Philppoff, J. (1993) *Decorative Paper*. New York: Mallard Books.
- Maurer-Mathison, D. (1899) *The Ultimate Marbling Handbook: A Guide to Basic and Advanced Techniques for Marbling Paper and Fabric*. Watson-Guptill Publications, Wentworth Books (Pittsfield, MA, U.S.A.)
- Medeiros, W. A. (1994) *Marbling techniques: How to create traditional and contemporary designs on paper and fabric*. Watson-Guptill Publications.
- Miura, E. (1991) *The Art of marbled paper: Marbled patterns and how to make them*. Kodansha International (JPN), 1st U.S. ed. Edition.
- Nastova I., Grupce O., Sukarova B., Turan S., Yaygingol M., Ozcatal M., Martinovska V., and Spirovska Z. (2012) Micro Raman spectroscopic analysis of inks and pigments in illuminated medieval old Slavonic manuscripts, *Journal of Raman Spectroscopy*, 43, 11, pp. 1729-1736, 10.1002/jrs.4084
- Nevins, I. (1989) *Traditional Marbling*. Sussex, NJ: Iris Nevins.
- Pazar, E.C. (2016) *The progress of the Art: paper marbling in the United States, 1880-1950*, MSc thesis, University of Delaware, Published by ProQuest Number: 10157412, <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:165094282>.
- Richard, J. (1991) *Marbled paper: its history and patterns*, University of Pennsylvania Press, Philadelphia, pp. 1-229.
- Rubovits, N. (1992) *Marbled Vignettes*. Los Angeles: Dawson's Book Shop.
- Schleicher, P and Schleicher, M. (1993) *Marbled designs: A complete guide to fifty-five elegant patterns*. Lark Books: Asheville, N.C.
- Schmoller, T. (1987) *An exhibition of Decorated Papers Paper Chase from the Schmoller Collection*, Edinburgh University Library.
- Shannon, F. (1987) *Paper Pleasures: The Creative Guide to Paper craft*. Weidenfeld & Nicolson in association with Il Papiro, New York.
- Sönmez, N. (2016) *Turkish Paper in 16th Century European Alba Amicorum. Two samples from the Stuttgart Württemberg State Library: Alba Amicorum of Georg Ringler and Johannes Weckherlin*, Ege University, Izmir, Museum of Paper and Book Arts.
- Wolfe, R. (1990) *Marbled paper: Its history, techniques, and patterns. With special reference to the relationship of marbling to bookbinding in Europe and the Western World*. University of Pennsylvania Press, Philadelphia.
- Woolnough, C.W. (1881) *The whole art of marbling*. London: Book Edges, etc. London: G. Bell.